

CONFLICT-RELATED SEXUAL VIOLATION: A WEAPON OF COERCION OF FEMALES IN BOKO HARAM TERRORISM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17225364>

Keywords:

Human rights violations, Forced marriage and sexual slavery, Legal frameworks on women's rights, Victim-to-perpetrator transformation, Qualitative historical analysis

Abstract: *Conflict related sexual violence is a pervasive, deeply troubling issue. Although it affects individuals of all demographics, it disproportionately targets females. In Boko Haram terrorism, females experienced intense gender-specific violence ranging from torture, forced marriage, sexual violations, and sexual slavery, acts which violated international human rights laws. The sect targeted and incorporated females into its war tactics as suicide bombers, and procreators of future jihadists. This article is an examination of how Boko Haram recruited young females into its movement, and weaponised them through coercion. It assessed the sect's use of conflict-related sexual violence as a weapon to coerce women into subservience, transforming them from victims to sympathisers, conspirators and perpetrators. It evaluated the lived experiences of these females, and the challenges they faced accessing justice in spite of existing legal frameworks on women and girls rights. Using the history method of qualitative research design, it gathered and analysed data from related secondary sources including books, journal articles, reports, and interviews from the media, relevant governmental and nongovernmental organisations. It submitted that females in Boko Haram were weaponised through sexual coercion, but that they remained silent and hard to reach. This was in part due to the ineffectiveness of existing legal frameworks which had little or no impact on the lives of the females in Boko Haram territories. It concluded that, sovereign states and intergovernmental organisations must acquire the will and capabilities to effectively protect the rights of females in Boko Haram terrorism, provide support for survivors, and hold perpetrators accountable.*

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Introduction

For many centuries women and girls have been targets of violent extremism.¹ Although violent armed conflicts inflict massive devastation on all humankind, plunging them into humanitarian crises and depriving them of fundamental human rights, they affect women and girls in very peculiar ways.² Gender-specific violence in conflict zones affects different categories of women, including victims of the conflicts, female combatants, and women as part of organised civil groups, human rights defenders and resistance movement.³ Their plights are multifaceted, spanning from general experiences such as the separation and loss of relatives to more specific ones like physical and economic insecurity as well as Conflict-Related Sexual Violence (CRSV).⁴ In Boko Haram terrorism, females were predominantly targets of CRSV, deprivation, abduction, physical and psychological abuse, forced marriage, forced labour, forced participation in terrorism operations, sexual servitude and slavery, forced

procreation of future jihadists.⁵ In some cases, the group uses these violations as tactics of war. Scholars of terrorism and counterterrorism have vigorously assessed conflict-related sexual violence and its attendant human rights violations in Boko Haram violent extremism. These academic works were centred on thematic concerns such as rape and sexual slavery, forced marriage, objectification of females, state and nonstate actors as perpetrators of transactional sex, and the difficulties getting accountability and justice for female victims. These works include John-Mark Iyi's *The Weaponisation of Women by Boko Haram and the Prospects of Accountability*⁶ that scrutinises women as weapons; Zenn and Pearson's *Women, Gender and the Evolving Tactics of Boko Haram*⁷ which examines the evolving tactics of the terrorist group; and Adeyeri and Aluede's *IDPs of Boko Haram War, Emergency Rehabilitation and Human Rights Practices in Nigeria*⁸ that probes human rights practices as it concerns internally displaced persons in the terrorism.

¹ Samer Muscati, "Women and Armed Conflicts," Human Rights Watch, published 2012, <https://www.hrw.org/topic/womens-rights/women-and-armed-conflict>.

² Charlotte Lindsey-Curtet, Florence T. Holst-Roness and Letitia Anderson, *Addressing the Needs of Women Affected by Armed Conflict: An ICRC Guidance Document*, (Geneva: ICRC, 2004), 8.

³ OHCHR and Women's Human Rights and Gender Equality, "Women's Human Rights and Gender-Related Concerns in Situations of Conflict and Instability," *United Nations Human Rights Office of the High Commissioner*, published n.d. <https://www.ohchr.org/en/women/womens-human-rights-and-gender-related-concerns-situations-conflict-and-instability>.

⁴ Lindsey-Curtet, Holst-Roness and Anderson, *Addressing the Needs of Women Affected by Armed Conflict*: 8.

⁵ Joe Read, "Sexual Violence and the Boko Haram Crisis in North East Nigeria," *Humanitarian Practice Network* 70, no. 8, (October 2017).

<https://odihpn.org/publication/sexual-violence-and-the-boko-haram-crisis-in-north-east-nigeria/#main>.

⁶ John-Mark Iyi, "The Weaponisation of Women by Boko Haram and the Prospects of Accountability," in *Boko Haram and International Law*, edited by John-Mark Iyi and Hennie Strydom, 259, (New York: Springer Publishing, 2018). DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-74957-0_12.

⁷ James Olusegun Adeyeri, and Jackson A. Aluede, "IDPs of Boko Haram War, Emergency Rehabilitation and Human Rights Practices in Nigeria," in *The Challenges of Refugees and Internally Displaced Persons in Africa*, edited by Sabella O. Abidde, 141-160, (Gewerbstrasse: Springer Nature, 2020). doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-56650-0_8.

⁸ Zenn, Jacob and Elizabeth Pearson. "Women, Gender and the evolving tactics of Boko Haram." *Journal of Terrorism Research* 5, no. 1, (February 2014): 46-57. <https://www.academia.edu/7100676/>.

However, these existing literature failed to evaluate conflict-related sexual violence as the weapon of coercion used to subjugate women into becoming tactical tools in the violent extremism. Using the history method of qualitative research design to fill this lacuna, this article drew data from two field reports from secondary sources: Report of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, *Violations and Abuses Committed by Boko Haram and the Impact on Human Rights in the Countries Affected*,⁹ and the Human Rights Watch field report, *Those Terrible Weeks in Their Camp: Boko Haram Violence against Women and Girls in Northeast Nigeria*.¹⁰ Accounts from victims in those reports were rigorously evaluated to gain some insight into their lived experience. Furthermore, findings from the reports and from other related secondary sources including books, journal articles, reports, interviews from the media, relevant governmental and nongovernmental organisations, were analysed. In its analysis, this paper argued that sexual violence was a weapon wielded by Boko Haram to force otherwise unwilling females into submission. It also argued that certain bottlenecks prevented domestic and international laws from providing justice to the

female victims of sexual coercion, and that conflicting discriminatory laws against women's right, impeded governments from ensuring females within Boko Haram's theatre of conflicts got the protection and justice they deserved.

Background on Boko Haram

Jama'atu Ahlis-Sunna Ladda'awati Wal-Jihad ("People committed to the Prophet's teaching for Propagation and Jihad), otherwise known as Boko Haram, founded by Mohammed Yusuf in 2002, is a terrorist organisation operating in four West African countries in the Lake Chad region: Nigeria, Chad, Cameroon and Niger.¹¹ Boko Haram has a reputation for gender-based violence and the weaponisation of women and girls as part of its war tactics, this trait connected it to terrorist organisations "in conflicts as diverse as Turkey, Sri Lanka and Iraq."¹² A number of events that occurred in 2014, revealed the nature of gender-based violence perpetrated by the group. In April 2014, Boko Haram kidnapped over 270 Chibok school girls, an event that announced its notoriety to the international community. In June 2014 the group joined the rank of terrorist organisations that weaponised females, when a middle-aged woman riding a motorcycle detonated a bomb strapped on her body at a military checkpoint. This was its first

⁹ United Nations General Assembly, *Violations and abuses committed by Boko Haram and the impact on human rights in the countries affected*, A/HRC/30/67 (Geneva: United Nations, 2015). <https://docs.un.org/en/A/HRC/30/67>.

¹⁰ HRW, *Those Terrible Weeks in Their Camp: Boko Haram Violence against Women and Girls in Northeast Nigeria*, (Washington D.C.: Human Rights Watch, 2014). <https://www.hrw.org/report/2014/10/27/those-terrible-weeks-their-camp/boko-haram-violence-against-women-and-girls>

¹¹ UN Security Council, *Jama'atu Ahlis-Sunna Lidda'awati Wal-Jihad (Boko Haram)*, (New York: UN, n.d.). [https://main.un.org/securitycouncil/sanctions/1267/aq_sanctions_list/summaries/entity/jama'atu-ahlis-sunna-lidda'awati-wal-jihad-\(boko\)](https://main.un.org/securitycouncil/sanctions/1267/aq_sanctions_list/summaries/entity/jama'atu-ahlis-sunna-lidda'awati-wal-jihad-(boko)).

¹² Mia Bloom and Hilary Matfess, "Women as Symbols and Swords in Boko Haram's Terror," *The Journal of Complex Operations* 6, no. 1, (March 2016): 106. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26470435>.

attack using a female suicide bomber. Women and young girls between ages 7 and seventeen were coerced into targeting large civilians gathering like bus stations, churches, mosques and markets.¹³

Conflict-Related Sexual Violence (CRSV)

United Nations Peacekeeping defined CRSV as a form of sexual violence directed at “an individual or group based on their sex or gender.”¹⁴ It refers to all forms of sexual violence directly or indirectly related to conflicts and includes sexual slavery, rape, forced prostitution, forced pregnancy, forced abortion, enforced sterilisation and forced marriage.¹⁵ In her report on 13 April 2022, the Secretary-General’s Special Representative working on ending sexual violence as a weapon of war, Pramila Patten says 3,293 UN-verified cases were documented in 18 countries in 2021 – 800 more than was recorded in 2020 – and 97 per cent were women and girls.¹⁶ Such progression she attributes to “the emboldening effects of impunity”.¹⁷ While CRSV can affect anyone caught in it, it affects women disproportionately.

Conflict-Related Sexual Violence runs contrary to the international human rights law as enshrined in several United Nations

Conventions including: Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women, Torture Convention, and Convention on the Rights of the Child amongst others. Nonetheless, in spite of various existing international and regional laws and policies to protect women’s rights particularly in conflict zones, reality is, they rarely benefited from these laws.¹⁸ Such was the case for females in Boko Haram terrorism.

Existing Legal Frameworks for Human Rights Law

Nigeria, Chad, Niger and Cameroon, the four states where Boko Haram had held sway are signatories to numerous human rights instruments and treaties designed to protect women and girls. All four countries have ratified and in some cases domesticated the following relevant treaties: The 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), adopted by the United Nations General Assembly Resolution 217 to protect the rights of every individual, everywhere. This was designed at the end of World War II in response to the “barbarous acts which have outraged the conscience of mankind.”¹⁹ Seven Decades down the line, the UDHR paved way for the adoption

¹³ Bloom and Matfess, “Women as Symbols and Swords in Boko Haram’s Terror,” 111-112.

¹⁴ United Nations Peacekeeping, “Conflict-Related Sexual Violence,” published (n.d.). <https://peacekeeping.un.org/en/conflict-related-sexual-violence>.

¹⁵ United Nations Peacekeeping, “Conflict-Related Sexual Violence.”

¹⁶ UN News, “Justice Critical for Fighting Sexual Violence in Conflict,” published 13 April 2022. <https://news.un.org/en/story/2022/04/1116192>.

¹⁷ UN News, “Justice Critical for Fighting Sexual Violence in Conflict.”

¹⁸ Rashida Manjoo and Calleigh McRaith, “Gender-Based Violence and Justice in Conflict and Post-Conflict Areas,” *Cornell International Law Journal* 44, no. 1, (December 2011): 12-14.

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/289005858>.

¹⁹ OHCHR, *Universal Declaration of Human Rights*, ST/DPI (02)/U59, (New York: UN, 1948). <https://www.ohchr.org/en/universal-declaration-of-human-rights>.

of over seventy human rights treaties some of which are women and girls oriented. These legal instruments at international and regional levels draw attention to women-based human rights issues. Most prominent among them is the United Nations Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW), adopted in 1979. CEDAW spells out what the obligations of the states are to ensure women can enjoy their rights to protection against all forms of discrimination including violence, poverty, lack of legal protections, access to credits, right to properties ownership and inheritance.²⁰ The Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment also known as the Torture Convention was adopted in 1984. The Torture Convention condemns any act that inflicts intentional pains on another human for whatsoever reasons including for the purpose of coercion or intimidation based on discrimination of any kind.²¹ Also, the Convention on the Rights of the Child was adopted in 1989 to protect children's right. It explained what children's rights were and what the governments' responsibilities were to protect them. And the Convention concerning the Prohibition and Immediate Action for the

Elimination of the Worst Forms of Child Labour or Worst Form of Labour convention adopted in 1999, stipulated the importance of education in the eliminating of the worst forms of child labour. While the Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the Involvement of Children in Armed Conflicts also known as the child soldier treaty adopted in 2000, concentrated on the right of the child in armed conflicts and orders its members not to conscript a child younger than 16 years into its armed forces and to ensure a child below 18 years does not take part in "direct hostilities."²² While the governments of the countries of focus in this article have ratified and domesticated these human rights treaties, conventions and legal tools, they still have in existence discriminatory laws governing marriage, inheritance, land and ownership of properties,²³ which presented as bottlenecks hindering effective implementations of these treaties and legal instruments. Some of these hold-ups were discussed in subsequent paragraphs.

Sexual Violence Against Females in Boko Haram

One feature that distinguished Boko Haram from other terrorist organisations was "the forced conscription and deployment" of

²⁰ UN Women, *Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW)*, A/RES/34/180 (Geneva: UN Women Headquarters, 1979). <https://www.un.org/womenwatch/daw/cedaw/cedaw.htm>.

²¹ OHCHR, *Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment*, A/RES/39/46 (Geneva: OHCHR, 1984). <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/convention-against-torture-and-other-cruel-inhuman-or-degrading>.

²² OHCHR, *Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the involvement of children in armed conflict*, A/RES/54/263 (Geneva: OHCHR, 2000). <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/optional-protocol-convention-rights-child-involvement-children>.

²³ "The Human Rights of Women," United Nations Population Funds, published 2006. <https://www.unfpa.org/resources/human-rights-women>.

females.²⁴ Forced conscription was a contradiction to what was obtained in other terrorist organisations that benefited from women's willingness to participate in violent extremism. The over one decade of violent conflicts dramatically transformed the lives of thousands of females, forcing some into, while others voluntarily embraced, new roles outside the sphere of lives they knew prior to the conflicts.²⁵ Some joined the terrorist group to escape their social conditions and ensure their livelihoods, others were coerced to join through abduction and enslavement.²⁶

Boko Haram intensified the patriarchal state of women and girls in their territories. This was partly because the north east of Nigeria was deeply rooted in patriarchy, with early marriage and high formal illiteracy rates defining the lives of women and girls.²⁷ Like other Islamic movements, the sect paid attention to the roles of women, however it projected differently such that while it further tightened "restrictions on them in some areas of life ... [it] also promoted their access to Islamic education and offered financial empowerment."²⁸ With no rights to determine their own choices in life, Boko Haram

use these women and girls for "political and pragmatic" purposes including to wreak havoc in communities, stage protests over the arrest of female relatives of some of its leaders, and lure military personnel into ambush.²⁹ They were also designated to birth future jihadists for the sect.³⁰

Females were aggressively coerced into the sect due to the value addition they offered in terms of tactics. Sequel to the first female suicide bombing incident in June 2014, there were a large number of suicide bombings of soft targets, all of them perpetrated by women and girls. The mere fact that they were females provided more than a few tactical advantages. They thrived on the "element of surprise," and took advantage of cultural reluctance to subject women to physical search, to evade detection. Also, symbolically, the death of female bombers evoked feelings of desperation and sympathy.³¹ In some circumstances, suicide bombings were carried out by rape victims, who were psychologically traumatised and without agency. According to Unicef report in 2016, one out of every five suicide bombings were done by children, and

²⁴ Bloom and Matfess, "Women as Symbols and Swords in Boko Haram's Terror," 107.

²⁵ International Crisis Group, *Nigeria: Women and the Boko Haram Insurgency*, N°242 (Brussels: International Crisis Group, 2016), 5. <https://www.crisisgroup.org/africa/west-africa/nigeria/nigeria-women-and-boko-haram-insurgency>.

²⁶ International Crisis Group, *Nigeria: Women and the Boko Haram Insurgency*, 2-3.

²⁷ Renée Ilene Pittins, *Women and Work in Northern Nigeria: Transcending Boundaries*, (Hampshire: Palgrave Macmillan 2002), 53. [doi:https://doi.org/10.1057/9781403914217](https://doi.org/10.1057/9781403914217).

²⁸ International Crisis Group, *Nigeria: Women and the Boko Haram Insurgency*, 5.

²⁹ International Crisis Group, *Nigeria: Women and the Boko Haram Insurgency*, 6-8.

³⁰ Ndahi Marama, "Boko Haram Rape 'Kidnapped Girls' to Give Birth to Future Fighters – Shettima," *Vanguard Nigeria Newspaper*, 4 May 2015. <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2015/05/boko-haram-members-rape-kidnapped-girls-to-continue-lineage-of-terrorists-shettima/>.

³¹ Bloom and Matfess, "Women as Symbols and Swords in Boko Haram's Terror," 108.

three quarter of these children were girls and they were often “drugged.”³²

Aside carrying out attacks, maintaining order within the camps, increasing the cohesion of terrorism and serving as bargaining chip with the government, females were also vessels for reproduction. Sexual violation was used as tool for population multiplication. Boko Haram deliberately ensure the procreation of the next generation of terrorists expected to keep the ideology alive. A former governor of Borno state, Kashim Shettima, captured it succinctly when he opined that the sect made conscious efforts to impregnate women, including praying before mating, “for God to make the products of what they are about doing become children that will inherit their ideology.”³³ Therefore, in a bid to raise a new generation of their kind, they waged “war on women’s physical, sexual and reproductive autonomy and rights.”³⁴ However, the group never issued a public statement on its reproduction campaign as it did when its founder Mohammed Yusuf, used the hadith narrated by Quranic scholar Abu Zayd, as justification for his proclamation that western education is sin that is turning children away from Islam.”³⁵

CRSV was suitable for Boko Haram as it fostered cohesiveness among its forced conscripted soldiers, while at the same time “undermining external social bonds and instilling fear” in the hearts of the locals.³⁶ Its human rights violations contributed to Boko Haram’s notoriety locally and internationally, as were documented in media, human rights, and humanitarian reports and assessments.³⁷ Yet, not much was really known about the abuse the women and girls endured in captivity. The lived experiences of some of the females, as was captured in the Human Rights Watch 2014 field research report, documented harrowing circumstances of some abducted females.³⁸ They mirrored the lives of thousands of other women held by the sect. Consequently, victims were mindful of social stigma and rejections would have suffer from their communities and families. Many opted to remain with their captors in the absence of effective social support, and justice system.

Nevertheless, it would be incorrect to argue that female suicide bombers for instance, were all coerced into a decision of self martyrdom or violent extremism. There were females whom of their own volition decided to martyr themselves

³² BBC, “Boko Haram crisis: ‘Huge rise’ in child suicide bombers,” 12 April 2016. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-36023444>.

³³ Marama, “Boko Haram Rape ‘Kidnapped Girls’ to Give Birth to Future Fighters.”

³⁴ UN News, “Condemning Use of Sexual Violence, UN Envoy Warns Boko Haram Aims to Destroy Family Structures,” published 27 May 2015. <https://news.un.org/en/story/2015/05/499942-condemning-use-sexual-violence-un-envoy-warns-boko-haram-aims-destroy-family>.

³⁵ Mohammed Sani Umar, “The Popular Discourses of Salafi Radicalism and Salafi Counter-radicalism in Nigeria: A Case Study of Boko Haram,” *Journal of Religion in Africa* 42, no. 2, (2012): 120. DOI: 10.1163/15700666-12341224.

³⁶ Read, “Sexual Violence and the Boko Haram Crisis in North East Nigeria.”

³⁷ Read, “Sexual Violence and the Boko Haram Crisis in North East Nigeria.”

³⁸ HRW, *Those Terrible Weeks in Their Camp*: 33.

or perpetrate terrorism for diverse reasons, although this was not always the case.

Challenges Accessing Justice as Victims of Sexual Violence

The pervasiveness of conflict-related sexual violence notwithstanding, historically, only on few occasions were perpetrators held accountable in formal justice systems, such as the Sepur Zarco case in 2016.³⁹ For survivors of Boko Haram's conflict-related sexual violence, access to formal justice were hindered by a number of factors including: gender bias and discriminatory attitude, social stigma, victims are hard to find, financial constraint, lack of effective accountability and lack of government funding.

Gauging the extent of the problem had major difficulties like: determining the number of abused victims, gathering evidence required by law to prove sexual abuse really occurred, and measuring the impacts.⁴⁰ Access to female victims was impeded because they were hard to find.⁴¹ Indeed, cases of sexual violence were underreported due to the culture of silence, the shame and the stigma attached to being sexually abused in the north-east.⁴² There was intense social stigmatisation on women who slept with

men outside marriage. Such incidents were shameful not only to the women but to their families. Females were subjected to “extremely high” stigmatisation, or rejected by their families or communities.⁴³ And children born outside wedlock are considered outcasts and in some cases they were ostracised alongside their mothers.⁴⁴

Other reasons included financial constraints. This remained a major factor why sexually coerced females in Boko Haram remained in such alliances. Victims of sexual violence are poor with low socio-economic status. With no source of income they resort to transaction sex as a means of survival.⁴⁵

In addition, a lack of “meaningful reporting channel,” and an ineffective accountability, have also resulted in less reporting and protest against abuse.⁴⁶ Many victims do not report their abuse to the police due to perceived lack of interest on the part of security agencies. As one abducted 22 year old woman puts it, “when others had reported to them in the past, they did nothing.”⁴⁷ Following closely, was the limited funding provided by governments and international donors for protection activities.⁴⁸ Government funding of military operations in terms of

³⁹ Claudia Martin, and Susan SáCouto, “Access to Justice for Victims of Conflict-related Sexual Violence: Lessons Learned from the Sepur Zarco Case,” *Journal of International Criminal Justice* 18, no. 2, (June 2020): 245. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jicj/mqaa006>.

⁴⁰ “Sexual Violence in Nigeria - Lives abandoned in the Name of Survival” International Committee of the Red Cross, published 2 May 2020, <https://www.icrc.org/en/document/sexual-violence-nigeria-lives-abandoned-name-survival>.

⁴¹ Read, “Sexual Violence and the Boko Haram Crisis in North East Nigeria.”

⁴² HRW, *Those Terrible Weeks in Their Camp*: 35.

⁴³ United Nations Peacekeeping, “Conflict-Related Sexual Violence.”

⁴⁴ “Sexual Violence in Nigeria - Lives abandoned in the Name of Survival.”

⁴⁵ “Sexual Violence in Nigeria - Lives abandoned in the Name of Survival.”

⁴⁶ Read, “Sexual Violence and the Boko Haram Crisis in North East Nigeria.”

⁴⁷ HRW, *Those Terrible Weeks in Their Camp*: 38.

⁴⁸ Read, “Sexual Violence and the Boko Haram Crisis in North East Nigeria.”

personnel and logistics are inadequate. Residents are poorly protected as security forces are sometimes overwhelmed due to insufficient manpower.⁴⁹ Consequently, victims of conflict-related violence remained hard-to-reach, and the crime, in spite of its prevalence and devastation, also remained invincible.

Bottleneck in Implementations of Legal Frameworks

Although there were numerous legal frameworks signed by Nigeria, Niger, Chad and Cameroon to address CRSV crimes, multifaceted barriers rendered them ineffective. They ranged from conflicting treaties, traditional international laws, to conflicting domestic laws. Certain complexities around state sovereignty prohibited external countries from carrying out military actions in another nation's territory without express consent. This limited the possible of interventions from the African Union (AU) and the United Nations.

While the principles of non-interference ideally protected the autonomy and integrity of states, in this instance, it can be argued that it was a bottleneck in the protection of the females in Boko Haram terrorism. Of course, it can also be argued that the provisions of Chapter VIII Article 53(1) of the United Nations Charter, empowered regional agencies such as the AU, to enforce actions⁵⁰. Scholars contended that,

regarding Boko Haram terrorism, Article 53(1) limited AU's powers to providing support to the Multinational Joint Task Force (MNJTF) of the Nigerien, Chadian, Cameroonian and Nigerian militaries mandated to fight Boko Haram.⁵¹ They also argued that the AU's mandate for the MNJTF failed to give adequate priority to the protection of women and girls.

The Statute of the International Criminal Court (ICC), is another international law that militated against the protection of females in Boko Haram. ICC Statute included rape and certain types of sexual violence in its list of war crimes against humanity. But, this was only if they were committed as systemic attacks against civilian populations. Crimes of sexual violence were also considered as international crimes against humanity, and acts of genocide or torture, since they were violation of international human rights law and international humanitarian law.⁵² But, CRVS crimes can only be categorised as such, if the armed conflicts responsible for their perpetration was recognised by the ICC as international in nature. In 2013, the ICC categorised Boko Haram terrorism as a non-international armed conflict, although it acknowledged that there are reasonable basis to conclude their activities amount to crimes against humanity.⁵³ Put differently, based on ICC's categorisation, human rights crimes

⁴⁹ HRW, *Those Terrible Weeks in Their Camp*: 37.

⁵⁰ United Nations, *Charter of the United Nations and Statute of the International Court of Justice*, (Geneva: United Nations, 2015), 35-36. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.18356/6261e8bc-en>.

⁵¹ Eki Yemisi Omorogbe, "The African Union, Boko Haram and Women in Crisis." *Ragion Pratica* 2, (2017): 439. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1415/88018>.

⁵² United Nations Peacekeeping, "Conflict-Related Sexual Violence."

⁵³ HRW, *Those Terrible Weeks in Their Camp*: 39.

perpetrated by Boko Haram do not qualify for trial because it is not international in nature. But, irrespective of categorisations, CRSV crimes were violations of human rights law and international humanitarian law, with widespread consequences. Its prevention must be treated as an “absolute priority” and not subject to probabilities.⁵⁴

At national levels, in Nigeria for instance, there are challenges on gender perspectives, existence of conflicting laws and complexities in the systems of government. These challenges posed legal bottlenecks in the implementation of certain conventions and treaties. For instance, the implementation of the Convention on the Rights of a Child. Nigeria runs a federal system of government. Therefore, while the Child Rights Act 2003 may provide extensive protection for children on conflict situations, prohibit child labour, child betrothal and early marriage, sexual abuse and exploitation of the child, this Act is only applicable in the Federal Capital Territory.⁵⁵ For the Act to take effect in the 36 states of the federation, each state’s House of Assembly must ratify it before it became operational.

Another challenge was a fundamental issue on the definition of a child? As enshrined in the Nigerian Constitution Section 29(4a), a child is any person under the age of eighteen. Meaning,

any person below the age of eighteen was consider by law to be a minor. In a sharp contrast however, Section 29(4b) goes on to consider any girl who was married as an adult.⁵⁶ By virtue of this law, a girl-child in early marriage to Boko Haram was an adult. The implications of this singular law were diverse as they were damaging. Under this law, underaged girls forced into marriage to Boko Haram members were considered adults, therefore, CRSV were not applicable to them. These bottlenecks made it difficult for females CRVS victims in Boko Haram to benefit from the protections international and domestic laws, or get formal justice.

Conclusion

Conflict related sexual violence (CRSV) targeted women in Boko Haram terrorism disproportionately. They were forced into marriage, sexual slavery and sexual servitude, which were convenient weapons of coercion that subjugated women into perpetrators, conspirators and procreators in the violent extremism. Although conflict related sexual violence was a prominent feature of the Boko Haram terrorism, related literature limited their study to female victimhood in the violent extremism, and did not examine how sexual violence was weaponised. This paper filled this lacuna by interrogating how the sect used sexual

⁵⁴ “Sexual Violence in Nigeria - Lives abandoned in the Name of Survival.”

⁵⁵ HRW, *Those Terrible Weeks in Their Camp*: 41.

⁵⁶ Nigeria National Human Rights commission, *Constitution of the Federal republic of Nigeria 1999*, (Lagos: Nigeria National Human Rights commission ,1999), 27. <https://nigeriarights.gov.ng/files/constitution.pdf>.

violence as weapon to control female members. It employed the history method of qualitative design to gather and analyse secondary data from two existing field reports and other related literature. It posited that women caught in Boko Haram terrorism in Nigeria, Niger, Chad and Cameroon were coerced into tactical tools through sexual violence. The study also argued that, despite the persistent conflict related sexual perversion in the sect, victims were unable to get formal justice due to fear of social stigmatisation and shame, the lack of effective accountability, and the difficulties in gathering required evidence to prove rape. Therefore, to mitigate the plight of female victims of CRSV, the Nigerian, Nigerian, Chadian and Cameroonian governments need to ensure they have access to hospitals equipped to treat post-rape care. They also need to make available public information on the physical and legal consequences of CRSV and how victims can access free and efficient services. Domestication of the International Criminal Court's Statute which criminalise CRSV under the Chad, Niger, Cameroon and Nigeria laws is an absolute necessity. Independent commissions of inquiry with niche provisions for victims of conflict related sexual violence in the Boko Haram terrorism, needs to be established to investigate human rights abuses. And, all states and provinces in all four countries need to pass into law and apply the Child Rights Act.

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Advance Journal of Current Research

Adv. J. C. Research

Vol. 10; Issue 9; September-2025

ISSN: 2323 – 1744

Impact Factor: 7.22

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/ajcr/index>

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